

AIRBORNE WIND TEST CASES

100 KW ISOLATED INLAND AWES TEST CASE

This test case evaluates the feasibility, performance and microgrid integration of a single 100 kW Airborne Wind Energy System (AWES), representing the first step in the AWES development pathway.

Site: [RWE's AWE test centre, Bangor Erris \(IE\)](#); economics also checked at [San Severo \(IT\)](#).

Partners: Polimi

TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

- The AWE system uses a tethered fixed-wing “windplane” that flies crosswind trajectories and generates electricity through on-board rotors (fig. 1).
- The 100 kW system features a 10 m wingspan, four rotors, a NACA-4421 airfoil profile, a weight of around 200 kg and a 150 m tether.
- The system’s development and assessment are supported by advanced modelling tools, including 1- and 6-degrees-of-freedom simulations, optimal control algorithms, engineering and aerodynamic models based on the vortex particle method, and a reference economic model for AWES (fig. 2).

Figure 1

Figure 2

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

- Flight operations are currently limited to altitudes of up to 150 m due to civil aviation regulations, affecting access to higher wind resources.
- From an operational perspective, microgrid integration requires stable power output and limited fluctuations.
- To address this challenge, power-smoothing control strategies have been developed, **reducing power variability to around 10% at the cost of approximately 5% energy loss**, thereby supporting reliable integration within microgrid environments.

RESULTS AND KEY FINDINGS

- The test case demonstrated the **strong technical and economic potential of AWES**. Results indicate a levelized cost of energy (LCoE) of approximately €31/MWh at the Bangor Erris site, comparable to conventional onshore wind, with an estimated payback period of around two years.
- The system achieved a **capacity factor of about 58% in Ireland and 32% in Italy**, remaining economically viable in both locations, with an annual energy production of approximately 508 MWh.
- The analysis also confirmed low capital and operational costs, while validating the effectiveness of closed-loop power-smoothing strategies for reliable microgrid integration.

LESSONS LEARNED

- Concurrent wing and onboard rotor aerodynamic design increases power production.
- A maximum-tether-stress constraint nearly doubles tether life at negligible yield cost.
- The technology remains competitive even at average wind sites with subsequent broad inland applicability.

SUSTAINABILITY AND UPTAKE PROSPECTS

- The results provide a foundation for the deployment of AWES in **off-grid and microgrid applications, particularly in remote locations**. The test case also serves as a key building block for the development of larger 1 MW and 30 MW AWES scenarios
- Long-term exploitation is supported through open-access datasets, modelling tools and the reference economic model for AWES, fostering further research, innovation and commercialisation opportunities^{1,2}.

¹ [A one-degree-of-freedom fly-gen airborne wind energy system model for power curve estimation - IOPscience](#)

² [Reference Economic Model for Airborne Wind Energy Systems](#)

1 MW INLAND AWES FARM TEST CASE

This test case investigates the feasibility of a medium-scale airborne wind energy farm composed of ten 100 kW windplanes, for a total capacity of 1 MW. The main objective is to **assess whether windplanes can be deployed at sufficient density to achieve power outputs comparable to conventional wind farms while minimising wake-related losses.**

Site: Maasvlakte 2, Rotterdam (offshore-like wind, inland logistics).

Partners: TU Delft, Polimi, DTU.

TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

This test case considers a farm of airborne windplanes based on the same 100 kW unit assessed in Case Study 1. The system operation and farm layout are analysed using an open-source AWE farm tool-chain that combines a one-degree-of-freedom windplane model, a Gaussian wake model, an economic assessment model and the TopDesign multidisciplinary design and optimisation framework. These tools support the evaluation of farm performance, wake interactions and overall economic viability.

DEMONSTRATOR ACTIVITIES

The test case builds on TU Delft's automatic-flight demonstration at Maasvlakte 2, where flights were successfully conducted at **altitudes of up to 900 m**. Wind resource assessments were based on data from the Dutch Offshore Wind Atlas, condensed into eight representative wind profiles. Farm performance was then evaluated for **three candidate layouts, focusing on efficiency and wake interactions under a reference wind speed of 7 m/s.**

On the right: Automatic flight demonstration at Maasvlakte 2 (TU Delft, 2012).

CHALLENGES AND ENABLING FACTORS

- A key challenge for airborne wind farms is **balancing installation density with the wake effects generated between neighbouring units**. Farm efficiency is strongly influenced by wind direction and the resulting interactions among windplanes.
- An important enabling factor is the use of a low-cost Gaussian wake model, which allows **efficient simulation and optimisation of farm layouts at scale**.

RESULTS AND KEY FINDINGS

- The analysis showed that airborne **wind farms can achieve power densities of up to 3.86 MW/km²**, comparable to conventional onshore wind farms (3–5 MW/km²). Among the layouts assessed, the **triangular staggered configuration proved to be the most land-efficient**, outperforming hexagonal and rectangular arrangements. The results also highlighted that **wake losses decrease significantly** and can effectively disappear above rated wind speed, supporting the scalability of the concept.

LESSONS LEARNED

The test case highlighted the **importance of farm layout design and trajectory management in minimising wake losses and maximising overall performance**. Results suggest that future deployments should prioritise optimised layouts and controlled trajectory overlap between units. A further lesson is the value of scaling up from a **well-characterised single windplane design**, ensuring consistent assumptions on power production, structural loads and economic performance across larger farm configurations.

SUSTAINABILITY AND UPTAKE PROSPECTS

The outcomes of this test case support the **optimisation and future deployment of airborne wind farms in both inland and coastal environments**. The developed methodology can be applied to larger-scale AWES projects, facilitating commercialisation and investment decisions. Further exploitation is enabled through the planned release of an open-source tool-chain integrating performance, wake and economic models for farm design and optimisation.

30 MW OFFSHORE AWES FARM

This test case evaluates the feasibility and aggregate wake effects of a **large-scale 30 MW offshore AWE farm**. The proposed configuration consists of thirty 1 MW windplanes, based on a scaled-up concept featuring a 30 m wingspan, deployed within the existing N4 (Heligoland) offshore cluster. The study aims to assess the **scaleability of AWES technology** and its potential integration into future offshore renewable energy developments.

Partners: DTU, Polimi.

TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

This test case considers a large offshore farm of airborne windplanes based on a scaled-up 1 MW unit. Each windplane features a 30 m wingspan, 3.0 m rotors, a mass of approximately 2,000 kg and a 450 m tether, enabling access to stronger offshore wind resources. System and farm performance are assessed using an open-source tool-chain that combines windplane dynamics, wake modelling, economic analysis and multidisciplinary design optimisation.

DEMONSTRATOR ACTIVITIES

The demonstration activities focused on **assessing the performance of a large-scale offshore AWES farm under different operating conditions**. Farm efficiency was evaluated at a reference wind speed of 7 m/s for multiple wind inflow directions, while the impact of wake interactions between units was analysed across a range of wind speeds. This approach enabled a **comprehensive assessment of farm behaviour and overall energy production performance**.

CHALLENGE AND ENABLING FACTOR

- A key challenge in large-scale deployment is the **increased wake interaction in denser offshore farms, leading to losses of around 14% in energy yield**. This highlights the importance of careful layout optimisation and flow management to mitigate inter-unit effects and maintain overall farm efficiency.

RESULTS AND KEY FINDINGS

→ The large-scale farm analysis showed an average power efficiency of approximately 0.86, corresponding to about 14% wake-related losses. Despite these interactions, the results confirm that the **system can be scaled consistently from 100 kW to 1 MW and up to 30 MW configurations** while maintaining predictable performance trends.

LESSONS LEARNED

Wake losses increase with farm size and density, but remain bounded, indicating that **highly dense offshore airborne wind farms are still feasible**. This suggests that large-scale deployment is technically plausible if layout design is carefully optimised to manage flow interactions.

SUSTAINABILITY AND UPTAKE PROSPECTS

The results highlight the **potential for adding capacity within existing offshore clusters with a relatively small additional spatial footprint**. This opens opportunities for hybrid configurations combining airborne wind energy systems and conventional turbines to support utility-scale offshore generation. Further exploitation is enabled through the planned open-source release of the integrated tool-chain, supporting continued research, optimisation and commercial development.

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